

Understanding eBird as a National Data Source in Belize

UB-ERI Brief
Nov 26, 2025

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Cite this Brief:

Boles, J. C., Ash, A., Perez, E., & Snaddon, J. L. (2025). Understanding eBird as a national data source in Belize. University of Belize Environmental Research Institute.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17742501

To support the understanding of species distributions, endangered species refuges, population trends, and changes in bird communities over time in Belize, data is our most important tool. eBird, which allows birders and the engaged public to record bird sightings through citizen science (Sullivan et al. 2009), is one of our largest national sources of bird biodiversity data. Here, we explore the eBird data availability and nature for Belize, and explore the opportunities to use this data to further scientific research and inform management decisions.

What is the Scope of the Data?

The eBird basic dataset (EBD) (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2025) is the core downloadable dataset which contains raw eBird data and metadata for observations and checklists. This includes all records for Belize, with the exception of four sensitive species (Orange-breasted Falcon [*Falco deiroleucus*], Scarlet Macaw [*Ara macao*], Yellow-headed Amazon [*Amazona oratrix*], and Yellow-naped Amazon [*Amazona auropalliata*]), which have their data excluded from the dataset for the protection of these species.

Belize's eBird data spans all the way back to the year 1905 with historical records, though it is not until the 1980s and beyond do we have consistently more than 100 checklists of a 5-year period. In the 2010s and onwards, more than 10,000 checklists were recorded each 5-year period, and currently, that number has climbed to 100,000+ (Figure 1).

As of November 15th 2025, the total number of verified checklists logged in the EBD for Belize is 325,660, encompassing 5,409,128 observations, by 25,880 observers. An additional 236 checklists hold data on eBird, but have been flagged by the eBird team as needing review by curators, due to potential issues in the data. These values do not include observations of sensitive species (e.g., endangered species and parrots/parakeets), as the data for these species requires special permission to access from eBird.

Figure 1. Number of Belize eBird checklists (\log_{10}) recorded by observation date, with binsize being 5-years.

Most of the observations come from traveling observations (3,614,808 observations), in which the observer moves around an area, recording each bird they see, and recording the distance (at least 30 m) and time travelled to capture effort. Stationary observations make up an additional 1,303,206 observations, being labelled as such when the observer stands within 30 m of a point and records all birds from that position. Here, effort is captured using time. Other observation types, such as incidental (241,043 observations; where a bird is recorded opportunistically) and historical (204,696 observations; where bird data exists, but data are incomplete), make up a smaller but still appreciable proportion of the observations.

The mean duration of timed observations was 110 minutes (IQR 31-135 min; median 72 min). For traveling observations, the mean distance traveled was 3.4 km (IQR 0.6-3.2 km; median 1.6 km). eBird recommends keeping observations under 3 hrs or 8 km to increase the precision of checklists, with the gold standard being less than 1 hr or 1 km (eBird, 2025). Thus, the available data adheres well to eBird recommendations. However, outliers in both effort categories drive up the mean, such as when people record checklists while driving and log very high distance traveled values. Overall, the mean number of observers participating in each checklist was 2.7 people (IQR 1-3 people; median 2 people).

Figure 2. Rank-abundance plot of relative abundance (proportion) by species rank.

in total, 605 unique species, as well as the 4 sensitive species not included in the data, have been observed in Belize. This total excludes hybrids, exotic escapees and purely domesticated species. The most commonly logged species are the Social Flycatcher (*Myiozetetes similis*) (98,396 times), Melodious Blackbird (*Dives dives*) (96,310 times), and Great-tailed Grackle (*Quiscalus mexicanus*) (92,278 times) (Figure 2). At the tail end, 16 species were observed only a single time, and only 51 species were observed fewer than 10 times.

Where in Belize is the Data Collected?

While all the districts of Belize have eBird data records, Cayo is strongly represented, encompassing over two million observations (2,296,936), compared to Belize district with 888,744, Orange Walk district with 765,265, Stann Creek district with 615,333, Toledo with 539,831, and Corozal with 303,019. Furthermore, data from within each district is not evenly spaced across the map, but instead is clustered around key hotspots, where data is continually contributed time and again (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Hexmap of Belize eBird observation density, with 20 by 20 hexbins, where hotter colors indicate greater density (log10 transformed) and cooler colors indicate smaller density. Protected areas are shaded in grey, and districts are separated by thick black lines.

Localities with the greatest contributions to the dataset include Black Rock Lodge (317,810 observations, 5.8% of total observations), Chan Chich Lodge (138,825 observations), and Chaa Creek Lodge (92,504 observations). Notably, these are all nature-based tourist destinations. In addition to tourist destinations, research and conservation areas, including Crooked Tree Wildlife Sanctuary, Toucan Ridge Ecology and Education Society, Cockscomb Basin Wildlife Sanctuary, and La Milpa Field Station also contributed greatly. This suggests that the most important contributors to eBird data in Belize include tourists and their guides, researchers, and rangers.

The percentage of observations inside protected areas is 23.1%, compared to 76.9% outside (Figure 3). A higher proportion of the data collected within protected areas may follow standardized monitoring methodologies, such as PROALAS (Programa de América Latina para las Aves Silvestres) (Ruiz-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2020). These sites may conduct annual monitoring or seasonal censuses; however, their sampling effort is less intensive than that occurring in tourist hotspots. To our knowledge, the protected areas that currently, or have, collected standardized eBird data either through ongoing research priorities or project-based monitoring include Cockscomb Basin Wildlife Sanctuary, St. Herman Blue Hole National Park, Tapir Mountain Nature Reserve, Guanacaste National Park, and Billy Barquedier National Park. Even with the standardized monitoring, the protected areas are underrepresented in the national eBird dataset, and PROALAS data only encompasses 1.6% of the total Belize observations.

Over time, the number of checklists has greatly increased (Figure 1). However, the number of observers on eBird has not matched this increase in pace for the key contributing localities. This is possibly due to these localities being tourist hotspots, and tour guides running checklists on their personal accounts for groups (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Line plot of number of checklists (A) and observers (B) by year for the top ten most contributing localities in Belize, indicated by color

What can we do with the Data?

With such an extensive, long-term dataset of Belize eBird observations, it leaves the door open for countless projects and analyses, which could contribute to our knowledge of species distributions and trends in-country. We can better inform conservation efforts (Backstrom *et al.*, 2024; Hatten *et al.* 2024), and look into key migratory patterns and habitats (Fern and Morrison, 2017; Gómez and Bayly, 2011). We can make inferences about trends in bird populations and communities over time (Bagwyn *et al.*, 2020), particularly in data-rich sites such as Black Rock Lodge, Chan Chich Lodge, and Chaa Creek. Data showcases about eBird patterns can be used for outreach and public initiatives to support avian awareness efforts. And of course, scientific projects on key topics of interest can be undergone, such as:

- Mapping seasonal and latitudinal distribution of a species of interest, such as the Ruddy Quail-Dove, or Shining Honeycreeper
- Identifying ecosystem associations, such as the Red Crossbill association with the Mountain Pine Ridge ecosystem
- Mapping ranges of endemic species
- Comparing bird community compositions inside and outside of protected areas
- Looking at the change in effort-standardized frequency of occurrence for priority species
- Looking at possible connections between land use change and bird community change over time, such as in developed or agricultural lands, which have replaced key habitats like broadleaf forest, savannah, or mangrove coastal habitat
- Looking at shifts in migratory patterns (such as arrival date) for key taxa over time
- Looking at functional group distribution across the country
- And much, much more!

This work would supplement work done by others both internationally and in Belize. For example, bird presence data from eBird coinciding with peak migration activity have been used to map critical areas for migratory songbirds (Fern and Morrison, 2017). The status of island-specific populations of Bahamian breeding landbirds has also been analyzed using 307,000+ eBird occurrence records (Bagwyn *et al.*, 2020). In Belize, species occurrence and stopover behaviour in Empidonax flycatchers during fall and spring migration in northeast Belize has been measured, using eBird data alongside mist-netting data (Gómez and Bayly, 2011). The results of these works have proven useful for understanding the ecology and population dynamics of birds in academia, and future research will no doubt expand that understanding even further.

While working on the data, it is important to remember the uneven sampling effort across Belize, with data being clustered at hotspots and centralized in Cayo district. Factors such as group size, observation protocol type, and whether the checklist was approved by the quality-control system should also be considered, as well as effort when appropriate, which can be quantified as duration or length of checklist. Observer skill variability is also a common limitation of eBird datasets, particularly for the detection of harder-to-identify species (Kelling *et al.*, 2015). It is also important for data users to note that some taxa classifications may vary between the eBird web application and raw data, such as rock pigeon being classified as wild on the web application and domestic in the raw data.

If you are a student or professional interested in working on the Belize eBird dataset, you can gain access by writing a project abstract and submitting it to the eBird platform for review. Should your abstract be reviewed positively, you will be given access. The UB-ERI is also open to collaborating on eBird projects, should you have an idea you are passionate about pursuing. Reach out, and let's talk! With data availability, critical thinking, and academic collaboration on our side, eBird is an important and powerful tool towards improving our understanding of Belize and protecting our natural heritage.

References:

- Backstrom, L. J., N. P. Leseberg, C. T. Callaghan, C. Sanderson, Richard. A. Fuller, and J. E. M. Watson (2024) "Using citizen science to identify Australia's least known birds and inform conservation action." *Emu – Austral Ornithology* 124(2): 199–205.
- Bagwyn, R., Bao, K., Burivalova, Z., & Wilcove, D. S. (2020). Using citizen-science data to identify declining or recently extinct populations of Bahamian birds. *Journal of Caribbean Ornithology*, 33, 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.55431/jco.2020.33.104-110>
- eBird. (2025). eBird rules and best practices. eBird Support. <https://support.ebird.org/en/support/solutions/articles/48000795623-ebird-rules-and-best-practices>
- Fern, R. R., & Morrison, M. L. (2017). Mapping critical areas for migratory songbirds using a fusion of remote sensing and distributional modeling techniques. *Ecological Informatics*, 42, 55–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2017.09.007>
- Gómez, C., & Bayly, N. J. (2011). Migration of Empidonax flycatchers through northeast Belize. *Ornitología Neotropical*, 22(3), 3.
- Hatten, C. E. R., Y. Y. Hadiprakarsa, C. K. F. Lee, A. Jain, R. Kaur, A. Miller, S. Cheema, N. J. Au, S. Khalid, and C. Dingle (2024) "Predicting conservation priority areas in Borneo for the critically endangered helmeted hornbill (*Rhinoplax vigil*)." *Global Ecology and Conservation* 55: e03206.
- Kelling, S., Johnston, A., Hochachka, W. M., Iliff, M., Fink, D., Gerbracht, J., Lagoze, C., La Sorte, F. A., Moore, T., Wiggins, A., Wong, W.-K., Wood, C., & Yu, J. (2015). Can Observation Skills of Citizen Scientists Be Estimated Using Species Accumulation Curves? *PLOS ONE*, 10(10), e0139600. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139600>
- Ruiz-Gutiérrez, V., Berlanga García, H. A., Calderón-Parra, R., Savarino-Drago, A., Aguilar-Gómez, M. Á., & Rodríguez-Contreras, V. (2020). Manual ilustrado para el monitoreo de aves silvestres. PROALAS: Programa de América Latina para las Aves Silvestres; Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad (CONABIO); Cornell Lab of Ornithology.
- Sullivan, B. L., Wood, C. L., Iliff, M. J., Bonney, R. E., Fink, D., & Kelling, S. (2009). eBird: A citizen-based bird observation network in the biological sciences. *Biological Conservation*, 142, 2282–2292.

Data Source:

Cornell Lab of Ornithology. (2025). eBird Basic Dataset (EBD). Version: EBD_relOct-2025. Available from <https://ebird.org/science/download-ebird-data-products> (Accessed: November 20, 2025).

R Code for Analysis:

Jessica C. Boles (sharp-lilac). (2025). ebird-analysis-belize (Version 1.0.0) [Computer software]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17727641>